

8T – Curvature Co-Products

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the primordial coupling constants series using category theory setting, it is possible to expand the idea of Bosons as part of a non-abelian gauge group of prime curvature. In contrast to previous papers which provided examples of addition, the emphasis will be performed on multiplication and co-products.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2. A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Let us analyze the product of two primes, which are distinct higher primes. According to the author proof of the Riemann hypothesis, primes form a non-abelian group, the condition under addition is to have an odd amount of primes under addition. Similar to the idea of quadratic curvature, we can present the idea of co-products of net curvature under multiplication.

$$N_{V1} \rightarrow N_{V1} \times N_{V2} \leftarrow N_{V2}$$

$$N_{V1} \times N_{V2} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$N_{V1} \times N_{V2} \not\cong N_{V1} \cup N_{V2}$$

In between each net variation element, we can define an automorphism arrow from itself to itself:

$$1_a : N_{V1} \rightarrow N_{V1}$$

$$1_a : N_{V2} \rightarrow N_{V2}$$

Since at high energies we can align the net variations elements on the same value, which in the case of the first three interactions lead to alignment at $N_V = +3$, and thus unification at $24 + 2$ variations.

$$8 + (1) + 2: [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3$$

The two real exchanges between the third and the first will modify the same middle element the exact same manner as presented in the 8T thesis. The only term we can vary is the left, as we want to ensure duality among the forces; we cannot touch the net variation, marked in black;

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3.$$

We cannot vary the invariant three; the modification will be to the left term in the coupling series;

$$(8 * 3) + 2 = 26$$

The physical meaning of such equivalence relation in high energy is a morphism between the Bosons. A gluon morphism the weak interaction W^+, W^-, Z Bosons, and photon morphism to the W^+, W^-, Z Bosons.

$$\gamma \rightarrow W^+ / W^- / Z$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + W^+$$

$$[8 + (g + 2)] \rightarrow 8 + W^+ / W^- / Z$$

it is possible to build an additional arrow from one independent element to another.

$$\Delta_1 : N_{V1} \rightarrow N_{V2}$$

$$\Delta_2 : N_{V2} \rightarrow N_{V1}$$

In general form:

$$\Delta : N_{VK} \rightarrow N_{VM}$$

Before the morphism they were distinct:

$$N_{VK} \neq N_{VM}$$

In the context of category theory, we have a category that has one class of objects, which vary in two ways, from themselves to themselves, from themselves to other objects in the class that are distinct, and are able to morph via addition and multiplication to other object in the class. The setting of category theory makes it simpler to understand the nature of Bosons, via arrows and morphisms, both are presented in the thesis in a mere numerical form. SEW unification in page twenty-nine, is a manifestation of the features of category theory and the morphisms among elements.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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